
APRIL 2020

TERMS OF REFERENCE FOR THE GOVERNANCE OF THE SUNRISE LARGE SCALE RESEARCH INITIATIVE

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D4.2

Terms of Reference for the governance of the SUNRISE Large Scale Research Initiative

Lead Beneficiary	Siemens/CEA
Delivery date	30.04.2020
Dissemination level	Public
Version	1.1

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 816336

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	816336
Acronym	SUNRISE
Start date of project (Duration)	01/03/2019 (12 months)
Document due date	28.02.2020
Submission date	30.04.2020
Authors	Siemens
Deliverable number	4.2

Deliverable name	Terms of Reference for the governance of the SUNRISE Large Scale Research Initiative
WP	4

Version	Date	Author	Description
v0.1	200220	T. Soller	Creation
v0.2	200408	F. Chandezon, M. Meier, S. Baumann	Review of WP team members
V1.0	200416	T. Soller, J. Kargul	Review from Quality & Impact Assurance team
V1.1	200429	T. Soller H. de Groot	Final version

PREAMBLE

Due to the termination of new Flagships in Horizon Europe, SUNRISE and the parallel CSA ENERGY-X merged in August 2019 and concertedly founded the SUNERGY initiative which was officially launched in February 2020. This was done in order to join forces towards the ambitious goals common for both CSAs. The particular embodiment and funding instrument(s) for the future SUNERGY Large Scale European Research and Innovation Initiative (LSERI) are under discussion at the time of writing of this document. Therefore, the proposed Terms of Reference for the future governance of SUNRISE / SUNERGY should be considered as provisional and need to be refined once the applicable boundary conditions are clarified.

This deliverable was created in close alignment with ENERGY-X to avoid a duplication of efforts for developing the future governance scheme. Consequently, the described governance structures in this deliverable are conforming with the governance setup in the corresponding report of the ENERGY-X consortium (Deliverable D5.3: Proposal on the ENERGY-X Governance structure).

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report amends the previous deliverable D4.1 - “Proposal for the organisational structure and processes of the SUNRISE large scale initiative” by providing further details and Terms of Reference for the identified governance bodies, both for the transition phase between the end of the SUNRISE CSA and the beginning of the SUNERGY LSERI (*i.e.* for the period from 2020 – 2024, termed “transition phase” or synonymously “ramp-up phase” in the following), and for the future LSERI itself (*i.e.* from 2024 onwards).

During the transition phase, the SUNERGY initiative will establish an interim governance structure based on a joint Executive Board (supported by a coordination office) and consultative Industrial & Scientific Boards to keep the stakeholder community actively involved and to continue the advocacy for a circular economy with sustainable fuels and chemicals. In order to fulfill those tasks, it is crucial to seamlessly implement the corresponding interim management bodies immediately after the end of the CSAs and maintain them until the boundary conditions and funding schemes for the future LSERI are clear. Funding of the transition phase will be accomplished on one side by collaborative research projects based on European calls and/or national instruments complemented by a CSA for the coordination activities. Before the start of the CSA (which is expected to start no earlier than 2021 with a dedicated call in Horizon Europe Work Programmes currently under discussion), the coordination activities of the SUNERGY initiative will be supported by a voluntary membership fee of the SUNERGY supporters complemented by in-kind contribution from some of the organizations involved the coordination of the overall initiative and/or national instruments for coordination activities.

For the long-term period, the temporary governance structures of the transition phase need to be amended and transformed into persistent bodies which can deal with the requirements of a LSERI. Based on the current assumption that the SUNERGY LSERI will be a co-programmed public-private partnership (cf. D4.1), the core elements of its governance scheme will be a Programming Board (for dynamic roadmapping as well as quality and impact assurance), an Executive Directorate (for the administration and the operational implementation of the overall initiative) as well as a common advisory board (for scientific, industrial and societal aspects) and a Funding Board.

For the Terms of Reference, a proper representation of all relevant stakeholders (*e.g.* from academia, industry, funding organizations) and – to the extent currently possible - compliance with the future HE framework was targeted. Nevertheless, further refinements of the governance structure and processes will be needed during the transition phase including well-defined mechanisms for joining or exiting the initiative.

D4.2 (Terms of Reference for the governance of the SUNRISE Flagship)

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AC - Associated Countries

CSA - Coordination and Support Action

DTU - Denmark Technical University

EC - European Commission

ESA - European Space Agency

EU - European Union

HE - Horizon Europe

IA - Innovation Action

LSERI - Large Scale European Research and Innovation Initiative

MPG - Max-Planck-Gesellschaft

MS - Member States

MoU - Memorandum of understanding

R&D - Research and Development

RIA - Research Innovation Action

1. Introduction

In the preceding deliverable D4.1, the governance structure of running Flagships and other European large scale initiatives was analysed and - after the decision to discontinue the Flagship instrument in the next Framework programme Horizon Europe (HE) – a tentative scenario for launching a SUNERGY Large Scale European Research and Innovation Initiative (LSERI) was explored based on other instruments and options (partnerships, missions) in the context of HE. That scenario formed the basis for the development of the Terms of References discussed in this deliverable.

In particular, the proposed scenario in deliverable D4.1 comprises:

- **a short-to-mid-term transition and “ramp-up” phase (2020-2024)** which will be used for i) implementing the blueprint, ii) strengthening and further developing the community including common coordinated activities according to the roadmaps and based on RIA & IA open calls complemented by national calls, and iii) the preparation of the subsequent LSERI. Since the conduction of those activities will not be possible without funding, a successor CSA project should be established with a duration of 3 years to bridge the time until the launch of the LSERI.
- **a long-term LSERI phase (after 2024)** which corresponds to the start of a SUNERGY partnership “*Fossil-free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy*”. Regarding the type of partnership, with both bottom-up (RIA) and programmatic (IA) components and the necessary flexibility in terms of composition of partners, objectives and activities, a co-programmed European partnership (cPPP) appears as the most suitable option. Besides having both public and private partners, the cPPP instrument also allows to have MS involved via the signature of MoUs and hence, to align national priorities with the SUNERGY roadmap.

The activities to develop the governance structures and processes for both the transition phase and the long-term phase were jointly performed between the ENERGY-X and SUNRISE consortia after the official announcement of the merger of the two CSAs in Aachen (Germany) on 20th August 2019. Two physical workshops and several electronic meetings were held between the teams dealing with governance definition to develop the joint proposal for the future organization of the SUNERGY initiative.

Consequently, the deliverables D5.3 (“Proposal on the ENERGY-X Governance structure”) of ENERGY-X and the present SUNRISE deliverable D4.2 (“Terms of Reference for the governance of the SUNRISE Large Scale Research Initiative”) are a co-production of both CSAs and were hence shared between the two consortia to make sure that both deliverables are consistent. Each consortium provided the necessary resources and did not duplicate the work done by the other.

This report hence uses the same figures and descriptions of the governance bodies as D5.3 of ENERGY-X, with minor updates (particularly regarding the Industrial Board) that emerged after the submission of ENERGY-X’s report.

2. Terms of Reference during the transition phase (2020-2024)

The proposed Governance structure for the transition phase with its respective bodies and instruments is schematically shown in Figure 1 and further described in the following paragraphs:

Figure 1. Scheme of the Governance structure for the transition “ramp-up” project phase, starting at the end of both CSAs until 2024.

Executive Board

Mandate of the Executive Board: The tasks and responsibilities of the Executive Board are the operational running of the SUNERGY initiative in the intermediate period with members having different roles and tasks which can be delegated upon need, *e.g.*:

- Development of a joint Manifesto,
- Outreach to EC/advocacy,
- Decision-making,
- Steering of transition phase,
- Finalization and implementation of the governance structure for the LSERI.

Composition of the Executive Board: So far, the two CSAs ENERGY-X and SUNRISE have mutually decided on the implementation of an active SUNERGY Executive Board for the transition

phase with 8 members: The Coordinator, Deputy Coordinator and 3 additional members of each consortium.

Coordinator: Prof. Bert Weckhuysen (ENERGY-X, Utrecht University, NL)

Deputy Coordinator: Dr. Frédéric Chandezon (SUNRISE, CEA, FR)

The other members of the Executive Board are:

ENERGY-X:	Prof. Gabriele Centi	(University of Medina, IT)
	Prof. Jens Nørskov	(DTU, DK)
	Prof. Robert Schlögl	(MPG, DE),
SUNRISE:	Prof. Huub de Groot	(Leiden University, NL)
	Prof. Joanna Kargul	(Warsaw University, PL)
	Dr. Carina Faber	(Université Catholique de Louvain, FR)

Coordination Office

Mandate of the Coordination Office: The interim coordination and management office is situated at Utrecht University providing administrative support and liaising with the EC and the SUNERGY community. All participating partners will be asked to financially support the initiative by paying a voluntary membership fee which will be utilized for management and coordination of the initiative and for communication activities. This membership fee will be maintained at least until other support for coordination activities is obtained, *e.g.* with another CSA.

Composition of the Coordination Office: The Coordination Office will be staffed with a Programme Coordinator who will be involved in developing, coordinating and implementing the strategic plan of the SUNERGY consortium, and who will function as the administrative right hand of the SUNERGY Coordinator and Deputy Coordinator.

Industrial Board

Mandate of the Industrial Board: The main role of the Industrial Board is to provide the views of industry on the overall development and strategy of SUNERGY. General coordinating tasks of the industrial board include:

- Alignment of the R&D program in SUNERGY with the industrial/economic needs (on short- to long-term time scale);
- Giving credibility to the need for the SUNERGY initiative and mobilization of industrial participation;
- Generation of proposals for the implementation projects (*e.g.* Innovation Actions).

Fulfilling these objectives include the following activities:

- Investigation of the market needs and forecasts as input to steer the scientific developments and joint R&I actions;

D4.2 (Terms of Reference for the governance of the SUNRISE Flagship)

- Provide input on pricing of synthetic molecules, expected quantities and economic needs, Capex/Opex/Efficiencies;
- Work on the desired value chain including handover points of molecules and needs for purification (and its costs) between the stakeholder. Define respective products and evaluate how the different industrial sectors can collaborate on industrialization;
- Work on modelling of the European energy system; provide input on energy storage needs;
- Align a European perspective on the circular economy with the worldwide view (e.g., what to harvest in Europe; future role of international energy exports etc.);
- Review the content of proposed research projects in view of market needs, time to market and acceptance of project outcomes for industrial and societal acceptance, focus to IA, accompany RIA;
- Monitor ongoing R&D activities (also on other frameworks) to avoid activities redundancy;
- Work with investors to help in making the output of the research bankable, which will provide the basis for an uptake of the research results in our future economy;
- Clearly communicate the economic value of the developments to national and trans-national funding agencies.

The industrial board will be actively involved in the discussion of the status and the developments of the SUNERGY research activities and technologies. Regular electronic meetings and yearly personal meetings (with the participants who can make themselves available) are going to ensure the communication and information sharing amongst the members of the Industrial Board. A copy of the meeting minutes will be shared with the Executive Board and the Scientific Board.

Composition of the Industrial Board: The composition of the Industrial Board should include all industrial fields of the SUNERGY value chain starting from the conversion of resources using system processes to base chemicals and fuels and their end use. The Industrial Board comprises 9 members including the chair. The members are proposed by the chair of the Industrial Board and validated by the Executive Board, and the composition can evolve after proposition from the chair validated by the Executive Board. The Chair of the Industrial Board is also member of the Coordination Office. The current composition of the Industrial Board is given below:

Chair:	Maximilian Fleischer	(Siemens Energy, DE)
Members:	Christoph Gürtler	(Covestro, DE)
	Marie-Godard Pithon	(VICAT, FR)
	Poul Georg Moses	(Haldor Topsøe, DK)
	Jan Mertens	(Engie, FR)
	Anastasios Perimenis	(CO ₂ Value Europe)
	Philippe Jacques	(EMIRI)
	Andreas Förster	(DECHEMA, DE)
	Alex van der Made	(Shell, NL)

Scientific Board

Mandate of the Scientific Board: Analogous to the Industrial Board, the Scientific Board shall provide inputs from the academia regarding the directions and future course of action of the SUNERGY initiative. This includes, amongst others, strategic advice on basic research priorities for the overall SUNERGY roadmap, identification of collaboration opportunities, and coordination activities concerning the generation of proposals for the relevant Research Innovation Actions.

Composition of the Scientific Board: The Scientific Board will contain members of the Member States (MS). They will join upon invitation from the Executive Board. All the SUNERGY relevant scientific fields, from fundamental to applied research, are going to be represented by various academic partners from all over the EU MS.

Task Force

Mandate of the Task Force: For active involvement of the Industrial Board and the Scientific Board a task force will be implemented. The Task Force will provide input and specific expertise for calls, assist in writing the research roadmap of the SUNERGY initiative and generally provide advice that aids the forthcoming of the project. The Task Force will report on the fulfillment of its responsibilities to the Executive Board.

Composition of the Task Force: The size and the setup of the task force will be decided by the Executive Board and can be revised on an as-needed basis.

SUNERGY Community

The SUNERGY initiative is additionally supported by a large group of stakeholders and supporters currently counting more than 300 institutions, companies, associations, governmental and local authorities, NGOs etc. SUNERGY will set up a community-building and networking platform for stakeholders to enlarge and strengthen the scientific, societal and industrial commitment. The SUNERGY community is always open for new members to get actively involved.

In order to support SUNERGY in terms of lobbying, networking and visibility enhancement activities, a small contribution in the form of a voluntary membership fee will be requested. The terms and regulations for participation are yet to be defined.

The Community will meet during an annual event/general assembly during which, the Coordinator, Deputy and members of the Executive and Industrial Boards will present and discuss the achievements and the general strategy to the community of stakeholders and supporters. Similarly, events will be organized at the national level gathering the national SUNERGY communities with participation of governmental representatives and whenever possible, the members of the SUNERGY boards.

Implementation of the SUNERGY Roadmap

The SUNERGY roadmap will be implemented by merging the two existing roadmap documents from SUNRISE and ENERGY-X into a single document. The research objectives and activities defined therein can be complemented by RIA/IA calls at the European level plus calls at the national level based upon the content of the SUNERGY roadmap. The framework and conditions for the calls will be determined by Horizon Europe (or H2020 if there are possibilities for adding SUNERGY topics based on the remaining budget).

All the granted projects should conclude a written collaboration agreement with the SUNERGY CSA and the other selected RIA and IA projects, and both the midterm review and the end evaluation of these projects shall be performed by the SUNERGY Executive Board operating under a mandate from the MS/AC and EC to prevent separation of authority from responsibility. Keeping the authority over the end result with the MS/AC and EC will ensure that both the RIA bottom-up components and the IA programmatic components contribute to the activities of the SUNERGY initiative.

Furthermore, for the communication and information sharing between the SUNERGY partners and for interested entities outside the initiative a comprehensive dissemination strategy plan for the joint SUNERGY initiative has been prepared together with the ENERGY-X communication partners.

3. Indicative Terms of Reference for the future SUNERGY LSERI (from 2024 onwards)

For the long-term period, the SUNERGY initiative plans to form an LSERI. The co-programmed public-private partnership was identified as one suitable instrument in the frame of Horizon Europe but could not start earlier than 2024. Due to the funding uncertainty, as discussions are still ongoing with EC and MS, all of the following considerations and descriptions of governance bodies are only indicative building blocks of the future SUNERGY LSERI governance structure. They need further detailing regarding the specific arrangements, processes and legal setup during the transition phase (2020-2024) by the Executive Board.

The proposed governance model of the future SUNERGY partnership is derived from the ESA structure. A schematic overview (cf. Figure 2) and a short, general description of its bodies and mandates are given below.

Figure 2. Tentative scheme of the Governance structure for the SUNERGY Large Scale European Research Initiative, starting in 2024

Funding Board

The Funding Board consists of the main public funders of SUNERGY, namely representatives from the MS/AC of Horizon Europe and the Commission. The main role of the Funding Board is to discuss and possibly plan the financial support to SUNERGY for the whole duration of the

partnership. The Funding Board is open to all MS/AC that are interested in SUNERGY, irrespective of whether they have SUNERGY-related policies and programs or not. Key objectives include:

- Exchanging information on the overall direction and strategy of SUNERGY;
- Linking SUNERGY roadmaps and blueprints to innovation policies at national and European level;
- Fostering synergies between SUNERGY and related activities funded at national, regional or transnational levels;
- Fostering international collaboration.

Programming Board

The Programming Board is central and acts as the main liaison body with the funding board, the SUNERGY community, the coordination body (*i.e.* the Executive Directorate) and the implementation part. It associates mandated expert members of the public and private stakeholders to plan the work and performs scouting in the community for new ideas worth to be developed further. The Programming Board steers the implementation towards its higher goals based on a mandated program with large-scale efforts (at higher cost) that need to be executed on time, and a bottom-up program that is bringing in the new developments. In order to have a balanced view, the Programming Board consists of representatives from EC and MS/AC, from academia and from industry (either via associations or single companies). As far as the latter, two stakeholder groups are concerned whose representatives can be chosen via an election process through the SUNERGY community for a temporary term.

Key objectives of the programming board are:

- Updating the overall roadmap and blueprint of SUNERGY based on the overall results obtained on the implementation part;
- Quality and impact monitoring, which includes selection of calls, review of proposals, evaluation of project progress incl. go/no-go decisions, and coherence monitoring;
- Securing of engagement and funding from the private sector.

Advisory Board

The Advisory Board could emerge from the Scientific and Industrial boards launched during the transition “ramp-up” period and should be complemented by a societal component. Such a board would have an advisory role both to the SUNERGY coordination and to the EC and MS. In addition, it would support and counsel the Programming Board regarding scientific, industrial and societal aspects. It consists of high-level independent experts and opinion leaders from academia, industry and NGOs and provides strategic advice and recommendations to the Programming Board. This includes the independent assessment of the SUNERGY progress and the review of the overall SUNERGY roadmap. The Advisory Board is open to participants from non-EU countries to enable global benchmarking of SUNERGY versus relevant activities outside the EU. The maximum

number of non-EU participants is limited to less than half of the overall size of the Advisory Board for keeping focus on EU priorities.

Executive Directorate

The Executive Directorate, headed by the Executive Director, is the coordination body of SUNERGY and acts as an intermediary between the SUNERGY community and the Programming Board. All administrative efforts regarding SUNERGY are handled via the Executive Directorate. This includes:

- Coordination, collection and processing of strategy input from the community via an open, transparent process;
- Regular communication and dissemination activities toward the SUNERGY community and the general public;
- Methodical support for the Programming Board;
- Holding of elections;
- Fostering networking and community building, for example via organization of an annual general assembly of the whole SUNERGY community.

The Executive Director will be supported by operational management staff (executive office). As operational day-to-day management of a LSERI is expected to be complex, it is likely that the executive office will run under an independent legal entity yet to be founded.

SUNERGY community

The SUNERGY community consists of scientific, industrial and societal stakeholders of SUNERGY's vision and mission. The community is always open for new members to get involved. In order to enter the community and take advantage of the benefits of SUNERGY in terms of lobbying, networking and visibility, applicants must sign a Memorandum of Understanding to confirm that they comprehend and acknowledge the principles of the partnership. The Memorandum of Understanding particularly stipulates common rules and criteria for the membership, *e.g.* regarding consortium formation, branding, information exchange, involvement and supporting of the Programming Board or resigning from the community. The SUNERGY community members contribute to the implementation of the overall SUNERGY LSERI roadmap and blueprint via participating in RIA and IA European calls or via national/local funding opportunities.

Be a change maker & Join our community!

@sunriseaction

@sunriseaction

SUNRISE – Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

SUNRISE – Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

SUNRISE – Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

www.sunriseaction.eu

c/o Leiden University
Einsteinweg 55 2333 CC Leiden
The Netherlands

Reach us at:
contact@sunriseaction.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336